
Method for the definition of fire ignition frequency based on type of ro-ro spaces in ro-ro ships

Eric De Carvalho, Matthieu Gadel, Léon Lewandowski, Antoine Breuillard, *Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore, France*, Corresponding author: eric.de-carvalho@bureauveritas.com

ABSTRACT

The increasing amount of data available in the maritime industry gives the opportunity to develop more and more quantitative risk assessments. In this study, a method to calculate a frequency of fire ignition in ro-ro spaces based on ship characteristics is established. Especially, the regression models built to predict the size distribution of ro-ro spaces are described. In order to verify the results, a benchmark on fire ignition frequencies is finally provided.

Keywords: *fire ignition frequency, ro-ro space, fleet database, formal safety assessment*

1. INTRODUCTION

Formal Safety Assessment (FSA) is a structured and systematic methodology, aimed at enhancing maritime safety by using risk analysis and cost-effectiveness assessment. It is used as a tool to help in the evaluation of new International Maritime Organization (IMO) regulations for maritime safety, while achieving a trade-off between maritime safety and costs (IMO, 2018).

The increasing amount of data available, especially in the field of maritime safety, gives more opportunities to carry out quantitative assessments. This enables the development of quantitative risk models and of general statistics, which provides a better understanding of the casualties and characteristics of ships under consideration. In that context, performing FSA studies with reliable data (transparent, comprehensive and available) (IMO, 2018) and structured databases is crucial. Moreover, the question of the quality of data and their limitations must be addressed.

Another challenge in an FSA study is the definition of a generic model that should

represent the fleet under consideration and which is generally limited to the selection of a generic ship. After reviewing the FIRESAFE studies, the IMO FSA Experts Group pointed out the dependency of the results of FSA study on the size and the arrangements of the three selected generic ships (IMO, 2019). The size dependency is handled into the EMSA 3 study (Konovessis, 2015) by performing the assessment for six generic passenger ships of different sizes and arrangements. A more unified approach could be to construct the risk model on parameters that directly takes into account the size dependency. For example, the ignition frequency is the first parameter that will feed a fire risk model. Such model exist and is widely used in other industries. Atkins for the Health and Safety Executive of the United Kingdom developed a method for the determination of on-site ignition probabilities based on ignition density (per square meter) for different type of usage areas (Daycock and Rew, 2004). In maritime industry, the project FIREPROOF managed to develop a probability of ignition model function of the floor area of an onboard space for passenger ships (Themelis, 2010). This is presumed to be much justified for ro-ro spaces since the frequency of ignition is

mainly due to the cargo (Wikman, 2016) and that the ignition frequency in that case ought to be an extensive variable, the more vehicles, the more frequent is the fire.

In the continuity of the FIRESAFE studies, the LASH FIRE project aims to develop solutions to enhance fire safety in ro-ro spaces by the development of innovative technologies as well as by the modification of operations and applications (LASH FIRE, 2021). An evaluation of each solution, in line with IMO FSA procedures, will be carried out within the project. One of the objectives of LASH FIRE's FSA is to refine what was initiated by the FIRESAFE studies and to define fire ignition frequencies per unit and type of ro-ro spaces. This manuscript is the summary of a wider study reported in a more detailed deliverable (Gadel, De Carvalho and Lewandowski, 2021). It focuses on the construction of the fleet database, of new features to estimate the size distribution of different types of ro-ro spaces and on the calculation of ignition frequencies per unit and type of ro-ro spaces. It will only address ro-ro passenger ships.

2. CONSTRUCTION OF THE FLEET DATABASE

In most of the FSA studies, one of the main purposes of a fleet database is to calculate the exposure time of the fleet under consideration in order to compute the ignition frequency. Generally in maritime industry, the exposure time is expressed in shipyear, which corresponds to the exposition of one ship during one year, considering the ship remain one full year in the fleet database conditions/criteria.

In LASH FIRE, the objective was no longer to calculate exposure times in shipyear but in unit of ro-ro spaces, lane meter-year for ro-ro passenger ships. However, no currently available database provides the number of lane meter per type of ro-ro spaces. A lane meter is a unit of measurement for a ro-ro ship's cargo space capacity, i.e. the total length of lanes. It is

measured in meters and the lane breadth is usually 3 m but this can vary about +/- 0.2 m.

2.1 Data source and scope of Fleet Database

Fleet and class history data purchased to IHS Maritime & Trade data were used as main source of information for the construction of the Fleet Database.

Ships in the Fleet Database were filtered according to the following criteria:

- Classed as ro-ro passenger ship;
- Delivered on or after 01/01/1970;
- With a Gross Tonnage equal or greater than 5000 GT;
- With a Froude number less than or equal to 0.5; and
- Classed or having been classed by an IACS member during their lifetime.

Delivery date. The approach of the FIRESAFE II study (Leroux, 2018) was used. It roughly corresponds to the adoption in 1967 by the IMO assembly of Resolution A.122, introducing the fire protection measures dedicated to passenger ship garage spaces.

Gross tonnage. Only SOLAS compliant ships were considered. Thereby, domestic ships, which are not necessarily compliant with the SOLAS Convention, were excluded from the database (except European Domestic Class A, which are SOLAS compliant, based on Article 4 of the Directive 2009/45/EC). In some FSA studies, a threshold of 1000 GT was used to separate domestic ro-ro passenger ships from international ro-ro passenger ships. In LASH FIRE, different thresholds were studied on a dataset of EU domestic and international ships provided by the European Maritime Safety Agency. A threshold of 5000 GT was considered the most appropriate threshold to separate international ships with ships having domestic-like behaviour.

Froude number. High Speed Crafts (HSCs) were excluded from the study, as they must comply with a specific regulation regarding fire protection. A ship is considered to be a HSC when the Froude number is higher than or equal to 0.5.

IACS-classed ship or which have been IACS-classed. Ships which have been classed by one of the IACS members at least once during their lifetime were considered. It is acknowledged that the maritime industry faces under-reporting of casualties (IMO, 2014), which can lead to an underestimation of risks. To address this problem, it is a common approach in FSA studies to consider only IACS-classed ships, on board which casualty reporting is deemed more accurate. In order to minimise the effects of under-reporting on the ignition frequency, this frequency was calculated as the ratio of number of casualties occurring on board IACS-classed ships over the exposure time of the IACS-classed fleet.

The resulted Fleet Database was not comprehensive for the calculation of an exposure time per unit and type of ro-ro spaces. Thereby, models were studied to complete missing values of database fields (total number of lane meters and passenger capacity) and to create new features (size distribution of ro-ro spaces).

2.2 Imputation of missing values

Considering the small number of missing values (1.7%) for the passenger capacity and that no clear correlation appears with other data, missing values were imputed as the mean of passenger capacity values (Equation (1) in Table 3). Missing values for the total number of lane meters were imputed as Equation (2) in Table 3. The techniques used to impute missing values will not be further detailed in this manuscript but the details can be found in the deliverable D04.2 (Gadel, De Carvalho and Lewandowski, 2021).

The root of the mean square error (RMSE) and the coefficient of determination Q^2 , which indicates how well regression predictions approximate real data points, defined by Leave-One-Out (LOO) cross validation are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Estimation of model errors

	RMSE	Q^2
Passenger capacity	692	-
Lane meter	454	0.66

2.3 Construction of new features: size distribution of ro-ro spaces

Three types of ro-ro spaces are defined in the SOLAS Convention: closed ro-ro space, open ro-ro space and weather deck. The objective is to propose an approach to estimate, based on ship characteristics, the percentage of closed ro-ro space(s), open ro-ro space(s) and weather deck(s) in terms of ro-ro lane meters.

The dataset used of the study was provided by ship operators from the LASH FIRE's Maritime Operators Advisory Group (MOAG), with the following data fields for ships of their own fleet (Table 2).

Table 2. Data fields provided by MOAG

Operator	Ship Name	IMO Number
Ship Type	Sister Ship	Total Lane Meters
Closed Percentage	Open Percentage	Weather Percentage

This dataset was filtered using fleet criteria, presented previously. The total number of ships in the filtered dataset was 146.

Table 3. List of imputation equations

$$PAX_{\text{missing}} = \overline{PAX} = 1080 \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} LM_{\text{missing}} = 190 \times GT_s - 210 \times PAX_s + 300 \times LPP_s + 210 \times B_s + 1300 \\ LM_{\text{missing}} = 100 \text{ if } LM_{\text{missing}} < 100 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where features were standardised and defined as:

$$GT_s = \frac{GT - 19000}{10000}$$

$$LPP_s = \frac{LPP - 140}{27}$$

$$PAX_s = \frac{PAX - 1100}{680}$$

$$B_s = \frac{B - 23}{3.6}$$

$$p_{\text{open}} = \left(\begin{array}{c} -0.77 \times GT_s + 0.89 \times LM_s + 0.39 \times PAX_s \\ -0.64 \times GT_s \times LM_s + 0.39 \times LM_s^2 - 0.34 \times PAX_s^2 + 0.38 \end{array} \right) \times 18 + 12 \quad (3)$$

$$p_{\text{weather}} = \left(\begin{array}{c} -0.62 \times GT_s + 0.91 \times LM_s - 0.4 \times PAX_s \\ +0.55 \times GT_s \times PAX_s - 0.64 \times LM_s \times PAX_s - 0.18 \end{array} \right) \times 9.3 + 5.9 \quad (4)$$

$$p_{\text{closed}} = 100 - p_{\text{weather}} - p_{\text{open}} \quad (5)$$

Where features are standardised and defined as:

$$GT_s = \frac{GT - 23000}{12000}$$

$$LM_s = \frac{LM - 1600}{880}$$

$$PAX_s = \frac{PAX - 1100}{600}$$

Figure 1 Distribution of gross tonnage for MOAG dataset.

Figure 2 Distribution of gross tonnage for the LASH FIRE fleet.

It is to be noted that an important number of sister ships was included in the dataset. When several ships share the same characteristics, only one of them was kept in the dataset to avoid any bias (training and error estimate). After suppression of all sister ships, the size of the training set for ro-ro passenger ships was 55 ships.

The distribution of gross tonnage of MOAG ships dataset is presented in Figure 1, along with the distribution of the entire LASH FIRE fleet (Figure 2). An over-representation of ships with gross tonnage comprised between 15000 GT and 35000 GT can be underlined in the training set. Nevertheless, it provides an acceptable representation of the entire LASH FIRE ro-ro passenger fleet, with a coverage of all gross tonnages.

At an exploratory stage, different types of classifications and regression models were investigated for the prediction of each percentage of ro-ro spaces based on ship characteristics. After estimating the prediction errors of different models and after considering the limitations of the dataset (number of data, quality, granularity, etc.), it was decided to further investigate polynomial regression models, as the other models did not provide significantly better results, and for the sake of reproducibility and simplicity.

As none particular correlation appeared between percentage values and ship characteristics, features of importance were identified by expert judgement. Those features are: gross tonnage, total number of lane meters and passenger capacity.

Polynomial transformations were performed on the standardised input features and the models were fitted by linear ridge regressions. Different sets of hyperparameters (degree of polynomial transformation, set of input feature) were studied for the prediction of each percentage. To avoid overfitting, a trade-off between the model results and the complexity (number of input, polynomial degree, etc.) was

considered. A polynomial model of degree 2 with input features gross tonnage, total number of lane meters and passenger capacity was selected and features reduction was further investigated on this model. Two independent models were considered for the percentages prediction (Equation (3) and (4) in Table 3), the third percentage being deduced from the two others (Equation (5) in Table 3).

The error was estimated by LOO cross validation as the RMSE. The total error for the prediction of the three percentages is defined as the average of the mean square error of each model. The errors for each model are presented in Table 4. Which means that, in average, the error performed by the total model of the three percentage prediction when performing on new, unseen data (LOO error) is 12.5%.

Table 4. Estimation of model errors

	RMSE
Closed ro-ro space	15.7
Open ro-ro space	13.5
Weather deck	6.25
Total	12.5

3. IGNITION FREQUENCY IN RO-RO SPACES PER UNIT AND TYPE OF RO-RO SPACES

3.1 Exposure time

Based on the results of the previous section, the size distribution of closed ro-ro space(s), open ro-ro space(s) and weather deck(s) in terms of ro-ro lane meters were estimated for each ship of the ro-ro passenger fleet. Thereby, the exposure time of each type of ro-ro spaces was calculated for the fleet by aggregation (Figure 3).

Closed ro-ro spaces are the most preponderant type of ro-ro spaces (78%) in the fleet, following by open ro-ro spaces (13%) and weather decks (9%).

Figure 3 Distribution of lane meter-years for the three types of ro-ro spaces in the ro-ro passenger fleet.

3.2 Ignition frequency

The number of fires in ro-ro spaces reported for the given fleet (not presented into this manuscript) was counted for each type of ro-ro spaces. The ignition frequencies per type of ro-ro spaces were calculated by dividing those numbers with the exposure time (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Frequency of fires in ro-ro spaces per type of ro-ro spaces in the ro-ro passenger fleet, per lane meter-year.

The ignition frequency in open ro-ro spaces (3.01E-6 per lane meter-year) is slightly higher (+25%) than the ignition frequency in closed ro-ro spaces (2.40E-6 per lane meter-year). Despite

a large difference in the exposure time, this result highlights that the likelihood of ignition for one lane meter of open ro-ro space is slightly higher than for one lane meter of closed ro-ro space. The ignition frequency on weather decks (8.57E-7 per lane meter year) is lower than for the two other types of ro-ro spaces. This may be because of its particular arrangement and environment making fire development more difficult. During a fire, heat and smoke are more likely to dissipate into the air, hence the fire will have less serious consequences than the ones reported and used for the calculation of the ignition frequencies. However, the result could also be a consequence of the sample size.

3.3 Verification

The ignition frequencies per unit of ro-ro spaces were applied to the generic ro-ro passenger ship, selected for the FSA study (LASH FIRE 1 in Table 5). The resulted ignition frequency per shipyear was benchmarked with the ignition frequency calculated with time exposure in shipyear (LASH FIRE 2 in Table 5) and with ignition frequencies from other FSA studies.

Table 5. Benchmark of ignition frequencies in ro-ro spaces for ro-ro passenger ships, per shipyear

Study	Frequency (fires per shipyear)
LASH FIRE 1 for the generic ship	5.35E-03
LASH FIRE 2 for the fleet	3.21E-3
SAFEDOR (2008)	0.99E-03
FIRESAFE II (2018)	5.28E-03
DNV GL (2016)	2.0E-03

The ignition frequency of the generic ro-ro passenger ship per shipyear is quite close to the ignition frequency calculated for the ro-ro passenger fleet, which confirms the selection of this generic ship as a fair representation of the fleet (at least in term of ignition likelihood). Despite different time periods, different databases and filtering criteria, the results obtained in the study are in the same order of magnitude as those from previous FSA studies.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a Fleet Database was built. Data imputation techniques were studied to create additional features missing from the initial dataset. In particular, significant work was done to develop models providing the size distribution of ro-ro spaces for a given ship based on its characteristics. Those new features enabled the calculation of exposure times per type of ro-ro spaces and, thereby, ignition frequencies per type of ro-ro spaces.

This manuscript only addresses ro-ro passenger ships but the same study was carried out for other types of ro-ro ships. Ignition frequencies per type of ro-ro spaces could be determined for vehicle carriers, however, not for ro-ro cargo ships.

The way forward for this study is to try to implement the ignition frequencies per type and unit of ro-ro spaces into the risk model. At the time of this manuscript, the quantification of the risk model has just started.

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6. DISCLAIMER

The opinions expressed in this manuscript are those of the authors and should not be construed to reflect the views of aforementioned organisations.

7. ABBREVIATIONS

EMSA	European Maritime Safety Agency
FSA	Formal Safety Assessment
HSC	High-Speed Craft
IACS	International Association of Classification Societies
IHS	Information Handling Services
IMO	International Maritime Organization
LOO	Leave-One-Out
MOAG	Maritime Operators Advisory Group
RMSE	Root of the Mean Square Error
SOLAS	International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea

8. NOMENCLATURE

B	breadth moulded, m
GT	gross tonnage, t
PAX	passenger capacity, passenger
LM	number of ro-ro lane meters, m
LPP	length between perpendicular, m
P_{closed}	percentage of closed ro-ro space(s) in term of ro-ro lane meters, %
P_{open}	percentage of open ro-ro space(s) in term of ro-ro lane meters, %
P_{weather}	percentage of weather deck(s) in term of ro-ro lane meters, %

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